

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

AN EXTENDED THICKNESS-DEPENDENT MOISTURE ABSORPTION MODEL FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

M. Johar, A. Azizan, K.J. Wong* and M.N. Tamin

School of Mechanical Engineering, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia,
Johor Bahru, Malaysia

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

INTRODUCTION

- Composite materials used in outdoor applications are inevitably subjected to environmental attack, which may lead to premature failure of the structures.
- Accelerated tests are usually conducted in laboratory. However, sometimes the amount of time needed to reach saturation is still relatively long, especially when **non-Fickian** behaviour is observed.
- Hence, there is a need to investigate the relationship between the moisture absorption behaviour and the **thickness** of the materials.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Material: **AS4/8552 carbon/epoxy composite**
 - Density of AS4 carbon fibre: 1.79 g/cm³
 - Density of 8552 epoxy resin: 1.30 g/cm³
 - Fibre volume fraction: 57.42%
 - Ply thickness: 0.13mm
- Stacking sequence: **unidirectional**
- Fabrication: **autoclave** at Composites Technology Research Malaysia (CTRM)
- Number of plies: **4, 8 and 16**
- Specimens size: **5×5 cm²** with sealed edge
- Water absorption test: **60°C** in **distilled water**

THICKNESS-DEPENDENT MODEL

$$\begin{aligned}M(t) &= M_I(t) + M_{II}(t) \\ &= \phi M_m G(t) + (1-\phi)M_m W(t) \\ &= \phi M_m \{1 - \exp[-7.3(D_z \cdot t/h^2)^{0.75}]\} + (1-\phi)M_m \{1 - \exp[-(\alpha \langle t-t_o \rangle)^{0.75}]\}\end{aligned}$$

FICTITIOUS FICKIAN

$$D_z = \pi \cdot [(1/(4 \cdot M_{m,F}))]^2 \cdot [(M_2 - M_1)/[(\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1})/h]]^2$$

$$M_1(t) = M_{m,F} [1 - \exp[-7.3(D_z \cdot t/h^2)^{0.75}]]$$

NON-FICKIAN FITTING

$$M_{II}(t) = (1-\phi)M_m W(t)$$

$$= (1-\phi)M_m \{1 - \exp[-(\alpha \langle t - t_o \rangle)^{0.75}]\}$$

$$\ln\{-\ln[1-W(t)]\} = 0.75 \times \ln\langle t - t_o \rangle + 0.75 \times \ln(\alpha)$$

No.ply	M_m (%)	ϕ	α (day ⁻¹)	t_o (day)
4	1.10	0.2923	0.0194	1.0
8	1.41	0.2286	0.0201	3.0
16	2.33	0.1378	0.0042	11.2

GENERALISED NON-FICKIAN PARAMETERS

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSIONS

- Thickness-dependent moisture absorption model:

$$M(t) = \phi M_m \{1 - \exp[-7.3(D_z \cdot t/h^2)^{0.75}]\} + (1 - \phi) M_m \{1 - \exp[-(\alpha < t - t_o >)^{0.75}]\}$$

- Non-Fickian Parameters: $\phi = 0.91h^{2-0.68}$, $\alpha' = 3.85h^{2-2.01}$ and $t_o' = 0.22h^{2.17}$.

FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

- Larger thickness - to find the upper limit
- Multidirectional laminates

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by Aerospace Malaysia Innovation Center (AMIC) through contract research grant No. 4C089 and Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) through matching grant No. 01M01.

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

THANK YOU

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22